

PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF EMOTIONAL TENSION DURING THE PROCESS OF ADAPTATION OF CADETS TO EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *This article reveals the psychological content and nature of the problem of emotional stress in the process of adaptation of cadets to educational activities. Also, this article presents a psychological comparative analysis of the state of emotional stress that occurs in the process of educational activities of cadets.*

Keywords: *cadet, adaptation, educational activities, emotional stress, psychological characteristics, comparative analysis.*

Introduction. The process of adaptation of cadets to the educational environment is a complex process that includes psychological, social and academic factors. The process of adaptation is mainly related to the new environment, discipline and specific requirements of educational activities. Personal adaptability and external support are important for this process to be successful.

As a rule, many consider the concepts of "emotional tension" and "stress state" to be one-dimensional, while others are used to distinguishing emotional experience according to the level of intensity. In fact, emotional stress should be interpreted as a specific form of emotional stress. Therefore, emotional stress is a form of reflection of difficult situations that are important for a person, prevent the successful implementation of activity goals, or are related to the possibility of endangering his life.

The main part. The main stages of the adaptation process in cadets include:

1. The initial stage is shock and understanding
 - New environment: Cadets get to know new discipline, strict rules and study conditions.
 - Challenges: During this phase, trainees may experience feelings of stress, anxiety, and fatigue.
 - Reactions: Initial contradictory reactions such as isolation, distrust or lack of motivation may be observed.
2. Adaptation stage - integration
 - Awareness of demands: Cadets begin to accept the demands of academic activities, physical loads and discipline.
 - Joining a team: Social relationships with peers develop and they understand their role in the team.
 - Gaining experience: Academic and practical skills are developed and confidence is increased.
3. Stable stage - internal reception
 - Self-expression: Cadets begin to feel comfortable in a new environment, actively engage in educational and team tasks.

- Increased motivation: Students actively strive to achieve success.
- Confidence: Cadets build confidence in their abilities.

Emotional stress and its causes, specific psychological research, psychodiagnostic assessment of them, development of psychological measures to prevent their occurrence, fear, anxiety, stress, form of emotional stress are listed, clarifying the nature of emotional states such as frustration, depressed mood and conceptual description is considered one of the most relevant works.

Researcher D. F. Kerner notes that in addition to physiological stress associated with physical difficulties, there is also a type of mental stress associated with evaluating stressful situations as dangerous and difficult.

F. Ye. Vaslyuk distinguishes two types of stress in his research:

1. Psychological stress;
2. Physiological stress.

Psychological stress is a person's understanding of the content of a stressful situation and always experiencing anxiety, fear, restlessness, and panic.

Physiological stress is a state of fatigue, sleeplessness, weight loss, fatigue, thirst, loss of appetite and even illness.

According to A.V. Otvetchikov, stress factors encountered in military activities include the following:

- According to the psychosocial and motivational content:
 1. Stresses of daily intense professional activity. This includes orders, various daily tasks regulated by regulatory documents.
 2. Emergency stressors. That is, performing specific military-professional tasks related to danger, threat, etc.;
 3. Stressors related to family life. Divorce, loss of loved ones, and family conflicts are also stressful factors.
 4. The situation of responsibility, i.e. performing tasks risking one's life for the sake of people's life and health, etc.
 5. Stressors in the content of the social environment. First of all, this is usually related to the separation of the cadet from his family environment, disconnection from social relations and distance from loved ones.

The term emotional exhaustion was introduced in 1974 by the American psychiatrist H.J. Freudenberger. This process ultimately involves characterizing the psychological state of healthy people, providing professional psychological support to clients and patients, and maintaining intense, intimate relationships in an emotionally exhausted environment. He defined emotional exhaustion as fatigue caused by the increased demands on one's resources and strength. Later, it was called this status-success disease.

According to the definition of the World Health Organization, emotional exhaustion syndrome is a physical, emotional or motivational exhaustion due to impaired work productivity, fatigue, insomnia, somatic diseases. Current stress problems related to difficulties in managing one's life are indicated in the international classification of diseases.

Initially, this term was defined as a state of helplessness, fatigue with a sense of one's own uselessness. According to modern researchers, emotional exhaustion can be related to the formation of chronic fatigue syndrome.

In 1980, C. Cherniss described the syndrome of emotional exhaustion as a loss of motivation to work in response to excessive obligations and dissatisfaction caused by psychological care and emotional exhaustion.

C. Maslach says that emotional arousal and loss of interest in work together with inhumane treatment of customers affects a person's professional identity and behavior at work. Later, he defined emotional exhaustion as a loss of interest and attention to work. In the future, these symptoms were accompanied by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a decrease in general work ability.

Thus, three main groups of manifestations of this condition were identified: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduction of personal professional achievements. Emotional exhaustion is usually understood as a feeling of emotional emptiness and fatigue that occurs as a result of professional activity. In this case, depersonalization is interpreted not as a classic psychiatric term, but as a decrease in personal participation in professional activities. Depersonalization is manifested in the form of dehumanization of the attitude to the objects of one's activity (patients/clients). In particular, it is possible to show coldness, formality of communication, rudeness and surveillance. The negative relationship that emerges may be latent at first and eventually manifests itself in inner turmoil that spills out and leads to conflict.

K.A. Abdulkhanova defines this condition as a mechanism of psychological protection in the form of complete or partial exclusion of emotions (reducing their energy) in response to psychotraumatic effects. In this regard, the feeling of exhaustion often seems to be an acquired stereotype of professional behavior, which allows a person to moderate and sparingly spend energy resources. By itself, V. V. Boyko considers emotional exhaustion to be constructive, and its consequences are dysfunctional, and this emotional exhaustion negatively affects professional activity and relationships with partners. At the same time, emotional exhaustion leads to professional deformation of the individual. Representatives of humanitarian professions and management staff: medical workers, managers, teachers, psychologists, sellers, lawyers, social workers, law enforcement officers are more prone to this situation.

Simplifying personal professional achievements leads to underestimation of professional success, a feeling of incompetence in one's professional field. Boredom is not a reaction to loss of creativity or boredom, but rather "emotional exhaustion caused by interpersonal communication and stress". According to S. Maslach, men are characterized by a higher level of depersonalization and dehumanization, and women are characterized by more emotional exhaustion. At the same time, it should be said that unmarried men are more prone to exhaustion.

A. Shirom et al (1989) consider emotional exhaustion to be a combination of physical, emotional and cognitive fatigue or exhaustion, where emotional exhaustion is the main factor. Additional components of burnout are the result of depersonalization, which is expressed in a decrease in personal achievements, or behaviors that lead to cognitive-emotional exhaustion (stress relief).

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that the secret of overcoming emotional stress in the educational activities of cadets depends on paying attention to the logic of this situation, quickly realizing the importance of stress in human life, psychological capabilities of the person and individual approach to the problem. In recent psychological research, two main types of stress are attracting more and more researchers' attention. The first is physiological stress, and the second is mental stress. Since a person is a social being, the mental sphere plays a leading role in his

activity, and this is often characterized by the type of stress that is important for the regulation process.

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